

QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES. PART XIV.

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In search for a potent and dependable amoebicidal drug, 8-ethoxyquinoline-5-amidine has been synthesised.

According to Payne (*Lancet*, 1945, *i*, 206) and other clinicians, the incidence of amoebiasis is surprisingly high, the diagnosis often difficult and elusive, the treatment unsatisfactory and the relapse rate disappointing. Derivatives of 8-hydroxyquinoline, such as Vioform, Chiniofon and Diodoquin, have been found to possess pronounced amoebicidal properties but none provides a guaranteed cure and there is therefore abundant need to discover more potent and dependable amoebicidal drugs.

In recent years much attention has been devoted to the parasiticidal properties of various amidine derivatives. The recent observations on the trypanocidal properties of various aromatic diamidines (King, Lourie and Yorke, *Lancet*, 1937, 233, 136; Ashley, Barber, Ewins, Newbery and Self, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 103; Kirk and Sati, *Ann. Trop. Med. Parasitol.*, 1940, 34, 82; Adams and Yorke, *ibid.*, 1939, 33, 323; 1940, 34, 174) have opened up a new line of research along which important therapeutic substances may be discovered. Paludrine, which is an amidine derivative of a type not hitherto met with in chemotherapy, has been found to possess pronounced antimalarial properties (Rose, Curd and Davey, *Brit. Med. J.*, 1945, 2, 653). In view of these observations on the activity of amidine derivatives against parasitic diseases, it has been considered desirable to prepare a derivative of 8-hydroxyquinoline containing an amidino group. Such a compound is expected to possess pronounced amoebicidal properties.

Attempts to prepare 5-cyano-8-hydroxyquinoline by heating the potassium salt of 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid with potassium cyanide at 250°, or to obtain directly the corresponding amidine derivative by heating the ammonium salt of 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid with a cyanide at 200-250° (*cf.* Oxley and Short, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 147) were not successful, 8-hydroxyquinoline being formed in each case. However, 5-amino-8-ethoxyquinoline (*Vis, J. prakt. Chem.*, 1892, *ii*, 45, 531) has now been converted into 5-cyano-8-ethoxyquinoline. This cyano compound has yielded 8-ethoxyquinoline-5-amidine (I), *via* the corresponding imino-ether hydrochloride.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

5-Nitro-8-ethoxyquinoline.—Vis (*loc. cit.*) obtained a mixture of 5-nitro-8-ethoxyquinoline and the corresponding dinitro derivative by nitrating 8-ethoxyquinoline (1 vol.) with fuming nitric acid (4 vols.). Under the following conditions only the 5-nitro-derivative has now been obtained in almost quantitative yield.

To 50 c. c. of fuming nitric acid (d 1.52) was added dropwise 8-ethoxyquinoline (25 c. c.) and the solution was allowed to remain at room temperature for 1 hour, then heated on the water-bath at 70-75° for 3 hours, cooled and finally poured into a large quantity of water. The resulting solution was then basified with sodium carbonate when a light yellow precipitate was obtained. It was filtered next day, washed thoroughly with water and was crystallised from alcohol (95%) in light yellow needles, m. p. 127-28°.

5-Amino-8-ethoxyquinoline.—The following method of reduction of 5-nitro-8-ethoxyquinoline has been found to be quite suitable.

To a solution of 5-nitro-8-ethoxyquinoline (30 g.) in alcohol (95%, 215 c. c.) water (55 c. c.) was added and the solution was mixed with iron powder (60 g.). The mixture was then heated on the water-bath under reflux in a three-necked flask fitted with a stirring arrangement, and hydrochloric acid (3.5 c. c. in 25 c. c. water) was added dropwise during 2 hours. After addition was over, the mixture was further heated for 2 hours, basified with sodium carbonate and filtered while hot. The filtrate was distilled under reduced pressure and the residue was washed thoroughly with cold water and was crystallised from hot water (charcoal) in yellow plates (16 g.), m. p. (when anhydrous) 114° (*cf. Vis, loc. cit.*).

Attempt to prepare 5-Cyano-8-hydroxyquinoline.—An intimate mixture of the potassium salt of 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (12 g.) and potassium cyanide (5 g.) was heated in a paraffin bath at 250° for 4 hours. On cooling, the fused mass was triturated with water and filtered. The residue was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and the solution, after being shaken with charcoal, was filtered. The filtrate, when basified with sodium carbonate, gave a precipitate which was crystallised from dilute alcohol in cream-coloured needles, m. p. 74-75°, and was proved to be 8-hydroxyquinoline.

5-Cyano-8-ethoxyquinoline.—5-Amino-8-ethoxyquinoline hydrochloride (35 g.) was dissolved in a mixture of concentrated hydrochloric acid (60 c. c.) and water (140 c. c.), and the resulting solution was diazotised at 0° with 1% sodium nitrite solution (100 c. c.). After 1 hour the solution was added with vigorous stirring to excess of cuprous cyanide solution and the mixture was then heated on the water-bath at 60° for 1 hour and left overnight. Next day the brown solid was filtered, washed thoroughly with water, dried in a hot place and extracted with boiling alcohol twice. The alcoholic solution on distillation gave a solid which was twice crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in colourless slender needles m. p. 129-30°, yield 14 g. (Found: N, 14.08. $C_{11}H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 14.14 per cent).

The *picrate* crystallised from hot alcohol in fine yellow needles, m. p. 172-73°.

8-Ethoxyquinoline-5-amidine (I).—Dry hydrogen chloride was passed into a solution of 5-cyano-8-ethoxyquinoline (3 g.) in absolute alcohol (8 c. c.) and dry ether (35 c. c.)

cooled in ice, and the solution was kept in a closed vessel in the refrigerator for 4 days. A small quantity of a light brown precipitate was obtained, which was filtered and was found to be 5-cyano-8-ethoxyquinoline hydrochloride. The filtrate, when kept in the closed vessel in the refrigerator for about 10 days more, deposited a light yellow precipitate (8-ethoxyquinoline-5-imino-ether hydrochloride), which was filtered, washed with dry ether and added to 15% alcoholic ammonia (50 c. c.) and occasionally shaken at room temperature for 4 days. The precipitate (ammonium chloride) was filtered and the filtrate concentrated under reduced pressure, when a solid (the corresponding amidine hydrochloride) was obtained. This amidine hydrochloride was then treated with excess of aqueous ammonia and the residual white solid was filtered, washed with water and was crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless rectangular plates m. p. 260-62°, yield 0.8 g. (Found in a sample dried at 120-125° in *vacuo* : N, 19.27. $C_{12}H_{11}ON$, requires N, 19.53 per cent).

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Received September 10, 1946.
